

The CCR5 Δ 32 Mutation Gap: The HIV Stem Cell Cure is almost irrelevant for Sub Saharan Africa

Policy and Research

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Abstract

The allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (allo-HSCT) cure for Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), achieved serendipitously through cancer treatment in a small number of individuals in Europe and North America, has been acclaimed globally as a landmark proof of concept. However, the scientific community's celebration of this development obscures a critical and largely unaddressed structural problem: the cure's underlying mechanism which is the CCR5 Δ 32 homozygous genetic mutation is virtually absent in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) populations, who bear over two thirds of the global HIV burden. This paper argues that the stem cell cure, as currently constituted, is almost entirely irrelevant to Sub-Saharan Africa on three compounding grounds: (1) the near-complete absence of the CCR5 Δ 32 allele in SSA populations renders donor matching biologically impractical (2) the procedure's extreme cost, complexity, and infrastructural demands make it logistically unfeasible in low and middle income country (LMIC) health systems; and (3) the cure was never intentionally designed for the global HIV crisis, it emerged accidentally from oncological care of a single White American patient in Berlin. Despite mounting evidence from subsequent cases, no coordinated international effort is actively developing a scalable, SSA-relevant cure pathway. This paper calls on the WHO to redirect research funding and policy attention toward scalable, population-appropriate HIV cure strategies.

Keywords: *HIV/AIDS; CCR5Δ32; stem cell transplantation; Sub-Saharan Africa; HIV cure; global health equity; hematopoietic stem cell transplantation; CCR5 mutation; antiretroviral therapy; genetic polymorphism*

Introduction

In February 2007, Timothy Ray Brown, a Seattle-born university student living in Berlin, underwent an allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplant (allo-HSCT) to treat acute myeloid leukemia (AML). His oncologist, Dr. Gero Hütter, recognizing that Brown was also HIV-positive, made the deliberate and unprecedented decision to screen potential stem cell donors for the CCR5Δ32 homozygous mutation, a rare genetic variant known to confer near complete resistance to HIV-1 infection. Among 267 tissue-matched donors identified for Brown, the 61st candidate tested positive for this mutation. The transplant was performed, antiretroviral therapy was discontinued on the day of surgery, and three months later Brown's viral load was undetectable. He would remain HIV-free for the rest of his life, dying in 2020 from a recurrence of leukemia. Brown became known to the world as the 'Berlin Patient' the first human being ever to be cured of HIV.¹

Since 2007, seven individuals have been reported cured of HIV following allo-HSCT procedures conducted in the context of treating blood cancers.^{2,3} Yet, as of 2026, not even one of these individuals was of Sub-Saharan African origin. And herein lies the central tension this paper examines.

Sub-Saharan Africa is home to two thirds of all people living with HIV worldwide. According to UNAIDS (2025), 40.8 million people globally were living with HIV at the end of 2024, with the overwhelming majority concentrated in Eastern and Southern Africa (52%) and Western and Central Africa (13%). In 2024 alone, Sub-Saharan Africa accounted for half of all new HIV infections globally, with adolescent girls and young women particularly at risk: of the 4,000 young women newly infected weekly, 3,300 were in Sub-Saharan Africa.⁴ Despite this staggering burden, the HIV stem cell cure offers virtually no direct therapeutic pathway for the populations who need it most.

This paper makes a tripartite argument. First, it establishes the genetic incompatibility: the CCR5 Δ 32 allele, which underpins the cure's mechanism, is essentially absent in Sub-Saharan African populations, making the donor pool for an SSA recipient effectively nonexistent. Second, it examines the procedural and structural barriers: allo-HSCT is an extraordinarily expensive, medically intensive, and infrastructure-demanding procedure that cannot be replicated at scale in the healthcare systems of most SSA nations. Third, it argues that the 'cure' was accidental, an opportunistic byproduct of cancer treatment in a privileged patient in a high-income country, and that no deliberate, funded, or coordinated scientific effort is meaningfully directed at developing an HIV cure strategy appropriate for African populations. The paper concludes with specific recommendations for WHO-directed action.

The CCR5 co-receptor and the Δ 32 mutation

HIV Entry and the CCR5 Co-receptor

Human Immunodeficiency Virus type 1 (HIV-1) infects host cells by binding to two surface receptors: the primary CD4 receptor and a chemokine co-receptor, most commonly CCR5 (C-C motif chemokine receptor 5). CCR5 is expressed on macrophages and CD4⁺ T lymphocytes, and its interaction with the viral envelope glycoprotein gp120 is essential for the entry of the predominant, macrophage-tropic (R5) strains of HIV-1 into target cells. This co-receptor dependency represents a mechanistic vulnerability in HIV's life cycle and has been the basis for CCR5 antagonists such as maraviroc, the only approved drug of its class.¹

The discovery that a 32-base-pair deletion in the CCR5 gene (CCR5 Δ 32) produces a truncated, non-functional protein retained intracellularly rather than expressed on the cell surface was a transformative finding in HIV immunology. Individuals who are homozygous for this deletion (CCR5 Δ 32/ Δ 32) express no functional CCR5 on their cells, rendering them highly resistant to infection by R5-tropic HIV-1 strains.

Those who are heterozygous (CCR5 Δ 32/wt) show partial resistance and typically experience slower disease progression if infected.^{5,6}

Cancer Therapy to HIV Cure

The discovery of the HIV stem cell cure was not the result of a targeted research programme aimed at curing HIV in the populations most affected by it. It was, by the admission of the central figures involved, an accident, more precisely, an opportunistic insight arising from an unrelated oncological emergency.

Timothy Ray Brown did not consent to a cure for HIV. He consented, reluctantly, to a life-saving stem cell transplant for AML, a rapidly progressing blood cancer for which chemotherapy had failed. Dr. Hütter was a hematologist with no prior HIV research experience who had merely 'read about' the CCR5 Δ 32 mutation and wondered what might happen if a CCR5 Δ 32-homozygous donor could be found among Brown's tissue matched candidates. The HIV cure was secondary to, and contingent upon, the cancer treatment. As Brown himself wrote: 'I did not need to be a guinea pig and risk my life receiving a transplant that might kill me.'⁷

The procedure nearly killed him. Brown developed severe graft versus host disease (GvHD), leukoencephalopathy, near-blindness, and temporary paralysis following his second transplant in 2008. A 2019 editorial in *The Lancet HIV* explicitly noted that the procedure Brown underwent 'is not scalable for people living with HIV' and 'can only be attempted in people with HIV and hematological malignant disease as a last resort.'⁸

The subsequent cases, share this same structural origin: all were individuals living simultaneously with HIV and a blood cancer requiring allo-HSCT. The cure of HIV was, in every case, a fortunate secondary outcome of cancer treatment. None of these individuals were from Sub Saharan Africa. None

were sought out because of the global imperative to address HIV in the populations bearing its greatest burden.^{2,3,8}

Genetic Evidence

Population Distribution of CCR5Δ32

The CCR5Δ32 allele has a well characterized and profoundly unequal geographic distribution. The mutation is believed to have originated in Northeastern Europe and is thought to be between 700 and 3,500 years old, with ancient DNA evidence suggesting an age of approximately 2,900 years. Its spread is closely associated with European population movement, and selection pressures from epidemic diseases such as smallpox or the Black Death may have driven its relatively high frequency in Northern and Western European populations.⁹

In European populations, the CCR5Δ32 allele frequency reaches as high as 16.4% in Norway and approximately 11.3% in France. In Northern Europe broadly, roughly 10% of individuals carry at least one copy of the deletion, and approximately 1% are homozygous - the genotype required for the stem cell cure to function as originally described. By stark contrast, the mutation frequency drops dramatically as one moves away from its European epicenter: it is rare in Asian and Middle Eastern populations, virtually absent in East Asian populations, and essentially non-existent in Sub-Saharan African populations.^{9,10,11}

Evidence of Absence in Sub Saharan Africa

The scientific literature on CCR5Δ32 allele frequency in Sub-Saharan Africa is consistent and unambiguous. A landmark study analyzing over 1.3 million hematopoietic stem cell donors across 87 countries found that CCR5Δ32 allele frequencies ranged from 16.4% in Norway to zero in donors from Ethiopia. Among the 27 country-level donor samples in which no individuals carried the homozygous CCR5Δ32/Δ32 genotype, the vast majority were from Africa, Asia, and South America.¹¹

A 2025 study from Angola published in *AIDS Research and Therapy* examined 284 individuals, both HIV-positive and HIV-negative, and found a CCR5 Δ 32 frequency of precisely 0% (0/272 alleles). The authors noted that the complete absence of the mutation was not surprising given existing literature, and that studies on this topic remain scarce in African countries despite the region's disproportionate HIV burden.¹² Studies on Nigerian and Zimbabwean populations found the same result: all 211 subjects examined were homozygous for the CCR5 wild type gene, with neither heterozygous nor homozygous CCR5 Δ 32 genotypes detected across any of the three major Nigerian ethnic subgroups.¹³ In Ethiopia, data from the Gondar population likewise showed a homozygous mutant allele frequency of zero.¹⁴

A donor pool for CCR5 Δ 32-homozygous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation simply does not exist within Sub-Saharan African populations. Even if every logistical and financial barrier were removed overnight, an SSA patient seeking the Berlin Patient type cure would need to source a CCR5 Δ 32/ Δ 32 donor overwhelmingly from European ancestry populations which would be a challenge of extraordinary complexity, compounded by the additional requirement for HLA compatibility.^{11,15}

The HLA Matching Compound Problem

Successful allo-HSCT requires high-resolution Human Leukocyte Antigen (HLA) matching between donor and recipient to minimize the risk of life-threatening graft versus host disease. HLA allele distributions are highly population-specific, meaning that patients are most likely to find compatible donors within their own ethnic group. Sub-Saharan African populations are among the most genetically diverse on earth, and HLA diversity in African populations is correspondingly high and underrepresented in international stem cell donor registries, which are overwhelmingly composed of donors of European ancestry.^{11,15}

This compound problem is, in practical terms, nearly impossible with current donor registries. Research modelling using DKMS donor data has confirmed that the probability of finding such a donor for a patient of Sub-Saharan African ancestry is vanishingly small.¹¹

Barriers to implementation in Sub Saharan Africa

The Prohibitive Cost of Allo-HSCT

Even in countries with the genetic preconditions for the cure, allo-HSCT is among the most expensive and resource-intensive medical procedures in existence. In high income countries, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation can cost between USD 100,000 and USD 300,000 per procedure, depending on conditioning regimens, donor procurement, post-transplant monitoring, and complication management. To contextualize this: the annual per capita health expenditure in many SSA nations is well below USD 200. First-line antiretroviral therapy has been brought down to approximately USD 50-100 per patient per year in some SSA settings through generic manufacturing and donor support.^{16,17,18}

The funding gap in the global HIV response stands at USD 3.2 billion annually. UNAIDS data indicate that external funding financed nearly 80% of HIV prevention programmes in Sub-Saharan Africa (funding now under severe threat) with PEPFAR commitments uncertain.^{4,19} Against this backdrop, the resources devoted to studying a cure applicable to at most a few thousand patients globally, while tens of millions in SSA remain untreated or undertreated, represent misallocation of global health research investment.

Healthcare Infrastructure Requirements

The allo-HSCT procedure demands healthcare infrastructure that is largely absent across Sub-Saharan Africa. Successful transplantation requires specialized bone marrow transplantation units with laminar airflow facilities; access to high-resolution HLA typing technology; advanced blood banking and

apheresis capabilities; intensive care units experienced in managing cytopenia, GvHD, opportunistic infections, and transplant-related toxicities; hematology and transplant medicine specialists; and long-term follow-up infrastructure. Most SSA countries lack one or more of these components, and many lack most of them.^{16,20}

The procedure is so medically intensive that even in the seven documented HIV cure cases, the process nearly killed several patients. Timothy Ray Brown had a 5% estimated survival probability during his second transplant. The notion that this procedure could be safely and routinely delivered across SSA health systems is, given present realities, fantastical.^{7,8}

The Dual Disease Prerequisite

An underappreciated barrier is that the HIV stem cell cure has been performed in patients who had both HIV and a hematological malignancy requiring allo-HSCT. The transplant was indicated by the cancer, not by the HIV. As Sharon Lewin, Director of the Peter Doherty Institute for Infection and Immunity, stated plainly: 'A bone marrow transplant is not a viable large-scale strategy for curing HIV, but it does present a proof of concept that HIV can be cured.' Carlos del Rio of Emory University concurred: 'This is not a scalable intervention.'^{18,20}

This means that even if all financial and genetic barriers were resolved, the cure would still only be applicable to a subset of HIV-positive patients who also have blood cancer, a comparatively rare coincidence. For the 25+ million people living with HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa who do not have hematological malignancies, the procedure as currently practiced does not offer a therapeutic pathway under any circumstances.

The absence of intentional, equitable design

The Berlin Patient case did not arise from a research programme designed to address the global HIV epidemic. It arose from the clinical necessity of treating a single White American expatriate's leukemia in a German hospital. Dr. Hütter was a hematologist, not an HIV researcher. The CCR5 Δ 32 insight was an intellectual extrapolation from reading, not from a funded programme of inquiry.^{7,21}

This accidentalism has not been corrected by subsequent research design. The field has appropriately recognized the Berlin Patient's significance as proof of concept and has invested in understanding the immunological mechanisms at work. However, the research architecture that has developed remains anchored to a European, high-income, CCR5 Δ 32-centric framework. The scientific community celebrates each new cure case, as it should. These are remarkable human achievements. But, unaccompanied by critical interrogation of who the science serves and who it excludes, risks becoming self-congratulatory.

When the WHO and broader global health community declare that an HIV cure has been achieved without simultaneously acknowledging that the cure is biologically inaccessible to the populations bearing the greatest burden, the implicit message is that a cure for the people who matter has been found. The millions in Sub-Saharan Africa remain, as always, secondary.

What Happened to the Cancer?

The question nobody has posed this whole time is, did the underlying cancer actually get cured? The answer is, ultimately no. This matters enormously, because the HIV cure and the cancer treatment are not separable events. They are the same event. If the cancer returns, the patient will die. The HIV cure becomes irrelevant.

Timothy Ray Brown's first stem cell transplant in 2007 achieved HIV remission but failed to eliminate the leukemia. A second transplant was required in 2008, which nearly killed him. He remained free of both HIV and cancer for over a decade, but in 2019, his leukemia returned. By 2020, the cancer had spread to his brain and spine. He entered hospice care and died on 29 September 2020, aged 54, not of HIV, from which he remained cured to his final breath, but of the very cancer whose treatment had incidentally produced that cure.^{22,23,24}

The symmetry is both medically instructive and morally sobering. The world's first HIV cure patient died of the disease that made the cure possible. The procedure did not confer lasting protection against cancer. Brown's oncologist acknowledged that 'a significant number of leukemia patients who have transplants will face cancer again, later in their lives.'²¹

Cancer Outcomes Among HIV Cure Patients

Among the seven documented HIV cure cases, the cancer outcomes are variable, and long-term prognosis remains uncertain for all. Three patients: Adam Castillejo (the London Patient), Marc Franke (the Düsseldorf Patient), and Paul Edmonds (the City of Hope Patient), have been reported as remaining in both HIV and cancer remission as of 2024, having received less intensive conditioning regimens than Brown. However, long-term post-transplant surveillance for haematological malignancies typically extends over decades, and remission at five or ten years does not constitute cure.^{2,3,25}

The HIV stem cell cure as practiced requires a patient to survive not only the transplant procedure itself but also the underlying hematological malignancy that necessitated the transplant. In Sub-Saharan Africa, where late-stage cancer diagnosis is common and post-transplant supportive care infrastructure is largely absent, these odds would be even less favorable. A cure that requires surviving a potentially fatal cancer treatment, in settings where that treatment barely exists, is not a cure in any operationally meaningful sense.^{16,20}

A Parable in Precision: The Cochlear Implant Analogy

To appreciate the full dimensions of the access problem the HIV stem cell cure presents, it is instructive to consider a parallel from another field of advanced medical technology: the cochlear implant. A surgically placed neuroprosthesis that restores hearing by delivering electrical stimulation directly to the auditory nerve, one of the most transformative medical devices of the twentieth century. And yet, disabling hearing loss affects an estimated 430 million people worldwide, with 80% of that burden falling in low and middle income countries. In SSA, the incidence of severe to profound congenital sensorineural hearing loss is five to six times higher than in the United States and Europe. Cochlear implantation, despite being technically feasible and clinically proven, has barely touched this population.²⁶

In Nigeria, costs associated with bilateral cochlear implantation have been quoted at up to USD 88,000.²⁷ In South Africa, the total estimated costs of pediatric cochlear implantation over the first ten years of use reach approximately USD 75,000.²⁸ In Malawi, even the annual cost of battery replacement represents an insurmountable expense for most families.²⁹ A 2023 scoping review found that in a country of over 200 million people, only 25 patients had been documented as recipients of cochlear implants across all available Nigerian literature.³⁰

The cochlear implant analogy illuminates the HIV stem cell cure's inaccessibility because it strips away the genetic uniqueness of the CCR5Δ32 problem and reveals a more structural truth, even when a transformative medical technology is not genetically restricted to particular populations, the healthcare systems of low and middle income countries in SSA are structurally incapable of delivering it at scale without deliberate, sustained, and targeted investment.

Emerging developments and missed opportunities

Moving Beyond CCR5Δ32

Recent developments in HIV cure science have begun to suggest that CCR5Δ32 homozygosity may not be an absolute prerequisite for sustained HIV remission following allo-HSCT. The Geneva Patient achieved remission following transplantation with wild-type donor cells. The second Berlin Patient achieved over five and a half years of HIV remission after receiving a transplant from a heterozygous donor.^{25,31} A 2025 Nature publication confirmed HIV remission of over six years in a patient transplanted with functionally active CCR5, suggesting that graft-versus-host and allogeneic immune mechanisms, independent of CCR5Δ32, may be capable of achieving HIV remission.³¹

This is scientifically relevant for, as it suggests that the donor mutation requirement may, in some cases, be relaxed. However, it does not resolve the other barriers: the requirement for concurrent hematological malignancy, the extreme cost, the infrastructural demands, and the HLA matching challenge all remain formidable obstacles.

Gene Therapy

Gene therapy approaches would, in principle, be population-agnostic, they would not rely on the CCR5Δ32 allele existing in a donor pool, and they could be applied regardless of a patient's ethnic background or genetic ancestry.³²

However, gene therapy for HIV remains in early-stage clinical trials, with significant unresolved challenges related to vector safety, off-target editing effects, transduction efficiency, and the elimination of established viral reservoirs. Critically, such therapies are being developed primarily in high income country academic and commercial settings, with little structured investment in the regulatory, manufacturing, and delivery infrastructure necessary to make them accessible in SSA. The history of antiretroviral therapy,

which took over two decades to reach affordable, large-scale access in SSA after its development in the West, suggests that without deliberate, proactive policy intervention, gene therapy cures will follow the same trajectory of delayed equity.^{19,32}

Policy Recommendations

The following recommendations are grounded in the recognition that the current HIV cure research landscape, while scientifically productive, is structurally misaligned with global health equity imperatives.

Commission an SSA-Focused HIV Cure Research Agenda.

The WHO, in partnership with the African Union, Africa CDC, and major research funders (NIH, Wellcome Trust, Global Fund), should commission a dedicated research programme specifically aimed at developing HIV cure strategies applicable to Sub-Saharan African populations. This programme must include systematic characterization of CCR5-independent HIV remission mechanisms; clinical trials explicitly enrolling SSA patients; and investment in gene therapy development pathways with built-in low income country access provisions from the outset.

Expand and Diversify Donor Registries.

International stem cell donor registries are overwhelmingly composed of donors of European ancestry. The WHO should support targeted drives to recruit donors from African, Asian, and Latin American populations, both to improve HLA matching prospects for non-European patients in existing transplant indications and to generate data on the feasibility of CCR5-independent cure strategies in these populations.

Invest in SSA Healthcare Infrastructure for Advanced Therapies.

The WHO, in collaboration with the World Bank and bilateral donors, should identify and fund the development of at least five regional centers of excellence in SSA with the capacity to conduct advanced

hematological and gene therapy procedures. These centers would serve both HIV cure research and broader oncological and hematological needs.

Establish Advance Access Commitments for HIV Cure Therapies.

Drawing on lessons from COVID-19 vaccine access inequities, the WHO should work with pharmaceutical companies, academic institutions, and governments to establish advance market commitments and tiered licensing frameworks that guarantee affordable access to HIV cure therapies in LMICs from the point of regulatory approval, not two decades after. Research conducted with public funding must be subject to public access obligations.

Explicitly Name the Equity Gap in Global Communications.

The WHO and UNAIDS must be explicit, in all public communications about HIV cure progress, about the populations to whom these cures currently do and do not apply. Celebrating a cure without contextualizing its inaccessibility to the most-affected populations is potentially harmful, as it may create misperceptions that suppress advocacy for more equitable approaches and reduce political pressure on funders to prioritize SSA-relevant research.

Conclusion

The HIV stem cell cure is one of the most remarkable achievements in the history of infectious disease medicine. Timothy Ray Brown's case, and the six cures that followed, proved something that many believed impossible: that HIV can be eliminated from the human body. That proof is significant. It has energized a generation of researchers, given hope to millions of people living with HIV, and opened new scientific frontiers in cure research.

But significance and relevance are not the same thing. For the 25 to 27 million people living with HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa, the stem cell cure is, as presently constituted, almost entirely irrelevant. The CCR5 Δ 32 mutation on which it depends is essentially absent from their gene pool.^{11,12,13,14} The procedure's cost and complexity are orders of magnitude beyond what their health systems can provide.^{16,17} And the cure itself was never designed for them, it happened to a White American man in Berlin, because his cancer doctor had a creative idea and the institutional resources to act on it.^{7,21}

The CCR5 Δ 32 mutation gap is a biological and a moral challenge. The WHO has both the standing and the responsibility to act accordingly.

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